

VARIATIONS IN THE ELECTROCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROGEN CLAY SOLS WITH TEMPERATURE*

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In a previous note (Mukherjee, Chatterjee and Sen, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 283) it has been shown that the free and total acids as also the degree of dissociation of silicic acid and hydrogen bentonite sols do not materially change with temperature between 1° and 50°. Variations with temperature of the free and total acids, degree of dissociation and the forms of the titration curves of hydrogen clay sol H, prepared from the entire clay fraction of a neutral calcareous soil from Government Seed Farm, Kalyanpore (U.P.) collected at a depth of 0 to 6 inches, are given in this note (Table I).

TABLE I.

Colloid content = 11.0 g. per litre.

p_a .			Free acidity $\times 10^6 N.$			Total acidity‡ $\times 10^6 N.$			a%.			p_H at inflexion.		
1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°	1°	35°	50°
5.07	4.84	4.61	0.96	1.5	2.5	286	286	286	0.33	0.52	0.87	9.05	8.25	7.75
4.97	4.79	4.60												

Unlike hydrosols of silicic acid and hydrogen bentonite, hydrogen clay sols show an increase of free acidity with a rise of temperature; but in agreement with the other sols they (sol H, fig. 1) give the same total acidity at different temperatures. The inflexion points, however, become displaced to higher p_H values with decreasing temperatures. The degree

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‡ Reproducible within $\pm 2\%$.

of dissociation, ratio of free to total acids, increases with temperature. Further work on this point with hydrogen clay sols is in progress.

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to titration at 1°, 35° and 50°.

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